

IMPROVING THE INTERFACE IN CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES WITH VARIABLE STIFFNESS

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ABSTRACT

Polystyrene-interleaved carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites with controllable stiffness have been manufactured that exhibit reductions in flexural stiffness of up to 99% when heated above the T_g of the interleaf layers. Flexural tests at room temperature indicate that improvements in adhesion between the polystyrene and CFRP layers are required to prevent premature flexural failure of the composites at low shear stresses. In this study we investigate how changing the interleaf layer can improve the flexural strength of the laminates through modification of the interleaf/CFRP interface. Two styrene maleic anhydride (SMA) films with different maleic anhydride content were chosen. Flexural tests showed that composites containing SMA interleaves had more than twice the flexural strength of composites containing pure polystyrene layers at 25°C and yet still undergo significant reductions in stiffness at elevated temperature.

1 INTRODUCTION

Much research has focused on the development of variable stiffness composites for use in shape adaptive structures [1-3]. Potential applications for these composites include their use as skin materials in morphing and deployable structures [1-3]. For these applications a composite material is required whose stiffness can be reduced on demand and which can then undergo large, reversible deformations. There are many designs of controllable stiffness composite. We showed previously that polyacrylamide (PAAm) coated carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites experienced reductions in stiffness of up to 88% when heated above the glass transition temperature (T_g) of PAAm [4]. This loss in stiffness was due to softening of the PAAm coating, which allowed the fibres to slide within the composite, thus limiting stress transfer between the fibres and the matrix. The stiffness was fully recovered when the composites were cooled to room temperature.

A number of studies have focused on the development of interleaved composites with controllable stiffness [5-8]. In a previous investigation we showed that polystyrene (PS) interleaved carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites could undergo considerable reductions in flexural stiffness when heated above the T_g of the polystyrene layers [9]. At these elevated temperatures the composites could be deformed significantly and would then fully recover upon removing the load.

A problem with interleaved composites is that the adhesion between the interleaf and matrix materials is often very weak, resulting in low toughness [10]. For example, polystyrene adheres poorly to the CFRP plies in interleaved laminates, which leads to the composites prematurely failing in shear during flexural tests. In this study we have selected an interleaf material (SMA) with better adhesion to the carbon fibre-epoxy layers than PS and show how this difference in adhesion affects the mechanical properties of the composites. For this investigation we used industrially manufactured PS films whereas in our earlier work [9] we used a batch scale process to manufacture PS films.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Materials

Pure PS pellets (PS 124N/L, Styrolution, Frankfurt, Germany) were supplied by TCKT (Wels, Austria). Styrene maleic anhydride pellets (XIRAN SZ 08250 and XIRAN SZ 15170) were supplied by Polyscope Polymers (Geleen, The Netherlands). For this study XIRAN SZ 08250 and XIRAN SZ 15170 are abbreviated to 50 PS and 70 PS, respectively. Hexcel (Duxford, UK) provided the unidirectional (UD) prepreg (Hexply 914C-TS-5-34%).

2.2 Film production

All films were made using a Plastik Maschinenbau PM 30 (Kelburg, Germany) equipped with a tapered screw (30mm diameter, 102mm long) and a flat film die. The temperatures within the machine at zones 1, 2 and 3 were 200°C, 220°C and 240°C, respectively. The temperature at the adapter (where the die is attached to the extruder) was 250°C and the temperature of the die was 260°C. The screw speed was set at 50rpm. The melt pressure was 30bar for pure PS and 45-50 bar for the SMA XIRAN grades. The take-off speed was 5.2-5.4m/min while the chill roll temperature was 70°C for pure PS and 90°C for the XIRAN polymers due to sample brittleness. The estimated throughput, calculated from film volume and take-off speed, was 7.2kg/h.

2.3 DSC analysis of interleaf films

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed on a Discovery DSC (TA Instruments, Eschborn, Germany). Samples were heated from 0°C to 300°C, cooled back to 0°C and then re-heated to 300°C at a heating and cooling rate of 10°C/min. All tests were conducted in a nitrogen atmosphere.

2.4 Composite production

The interleaved laminates consisted of 8 interleaf layers and 9 CFRP layers (each layer consisting of 1 ply) arranged in alternating sequence. A pure CFRP 0° control laminate consisting of 16 plies was also manufactured. The composite plates were 100mm × 150mm with the 0° fibre direction parallel to the 100mm side. The composite panels were cured in an autoclave (Quicklock Thermoclave, LBBC, Leeds, UK) at 175°C and 100psi for 1hour.

2.5 Preparation of DMTA and flexural test specimens

The cured panels were cut into 80mm × 10mm specimens for flexural testing and 50mm × 10mm specimens for DMTA using a dry diamond bladed cutter (Tilt Arbour Saw, Startrite, Derbyshire, UK). The 0° direction was parallel to the longer specimen dimension in all cases.

2.6 DMTA of composites

The composite specimens were tested using an RSA-G2 (TA Instruments, Eschborn, Germany) in 3-point bending from 30°C to 230°C and at a heating rate of 5°C/min. The frequency was set at 1Hz.

2.7 Flexural tests

The flexural properties of the composites were determined at room and elevated temperature (140°C) using three point bending tests in accordance with ASTM D7264-07. The tests were performed on an Instron 5985 (Bucks, UK) with a 10 kN load cell. A 32:1 span-to-thickness ratio and a crosshead speed of 1mm/min were used. The loading nose and supports had a diameter of 6mm. Specimens were loaded at room temperature (RT1) to a maximum deflection of 1mm and then unloaded. The tests were then repeated in an environmental chamber (SFL, Eurotherm, West Sussex, UK) at 140°C and then again at room temperature (RT2). Eq.1 was used to calculate the apparent flexural modulus E_f of the specimens, where L is the support span, b the beam width, h the beam thickness and m the gradient of the linear portion of the load - displacement curve between zero and 1 mm displacement. Five specimens of each sample were tested to calculate the average flexural modulus of the composites.

$$E_f = \frac{L^3 m}{4bh^3} \quad (1)$$

To determine the flexural strength, previously untested specimens were loaded to failure at room temperature. Eq.2 was used to calculate the apparent flexural strength, where σ is the maximum stress at the outer surface at the mid-span of the specimen (MPa) and P the applied force at failure (N). Five specimens were loaded to failure to determine the apparent flexural strength of each sample.

$$\sigma = \frac{3PL}{2bh^2} \quad (2)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermal properties of interleaf films

The glass transition temperatures of the interleaf films were recorded using DSC. The T_g of the pure PS, 50 PS and 70 PS films were 87°C, 111°C and 127°C, respectively. The difference in T_g for the two SMA films was due to variations in molecular weight and MAH content.

3.2 Viscoelastic properties of composites

The pure CFRP composite has a single T_g at 191°C that corresponds to that of the epoxy resin (Figure 1). The storage modulus at 30°C was 93 GPa and the initial stiffness loss occurred at approximately 120°C. The interleaved composite containing pure polystyrene layers had a storage modulus of 61 GPa at 30°C, which dropped by 98% to 1 GPa when heated through the T_g of PS to 140°C. The composite containing 50 PS interleaves had a storage modulus of 67 GPa at 30°C. When the composites were heated to 140°C the stiffness dropped by 97% to 2 GPa. The 70 PS-interleaved composite underwent a 60% loss in stiffness from 58 GPa at 30°C to 23 GPa at 140°C. The reduction in stiffness for the 70 PS-interleaved composite was less than that of the other composites as the interleaf layer had not fully softened at 140°C.

Figure 1: DMTA curves showing the storage modulus (E'), loss modulus (E'') and $\tan \delta$ as a function of temperature for (a) pure CFRP (b) pure PS (c) 50 PS and (d) 70 PS-interleaved laminates.

3.3 Flexural properties of composites

At room temperature the pure PS-interleaved specimens had an apparent flexural strength of 382 ± 29 MPa (Table 1) and failed in interlaminar shear. The 50 PS and 70 PS-interleaved composites had flexural strengths at RT of 1107 ± 38 MPa and 1002 ± 17 MPa, respectively. This increase in strength was due to improved bonding at the interleaf/CFRP interface. These composites failed in fracture on the compressive side which led to interlaminar shear and also showed breaking of the outer fibres on the tensile side. At RT the pure CFRP composite had a flexural strength of 1814 ± 80 MPa and failed in compression at the mid-span. Flexural strength vs. flexural modulus at RT for each laminate is shown in Figure 2. At HT, the pure PS-interleaved laminate bent under the load without failing, however the load attained was lower than that of the other composites. A flexural strength for this composite could not be recorded at HT due to limitations with the testing equipment at high specimen deflections. The 50 PS-interleaved laminate had a flexural strength of 82 ± 2 MPa at 140°C . The composites showed formation of micro-cracks between the loading nose and supports. The 70 PS-interleaved laminate had a flexural strength of 187 ± 12 MPa at HT and failed in compression at the mid-span. Unlike the pure PS-interleaved composite, these laminates failed at 140°C because of improved bonding at the interface that restricted deformation of the interleaf layers.

The apparent flexural modulus of the 16-ply 0° control sample was 119 ± 6 GPa at room temperature. There was no reduction in stiffness when the specimens were heated to 140°C . The pure PS-interleaved composites had an apparent flexural modulus of 56 ± 1 GPa at RT which fell by 99% to 0.4 ± 0.1 GPa at 140°C . The apparent flexural modulus of the 50 PS composite at RT was 66 ± 4

GPa. When heated to 140°C there was a 95% reduction in stiffness to 3 ± 0.1 GPa. The 70 PS composite underwent an 84% loss in stiffness from 64 ± 3 GPa at RT to 10 ± 2 GPa at 140°C. Again, this reduction in stiffness was lower than that of the other composites as the interleaf layers had not fully softened.

Composite	Flexural strength/ MPa			Flexural modulus/ GPa		
	RT1 [†]	140°C	% loss	RT1	140°C	% loss
16-ply 0° control	1814 ± 80	714 ± 173	61	119 ± 6	121 ± 3	-
Pure PS-interleaved	382 ± 29	-	-	56 ± 1	0.4 ± 0.1	99
50 PS-interleaved	1107 ± 38	82 ± 2	93	66 ± 4	3 ± 0.1	95
70 PS-interleaved	1002 ± 17	187 ± 12	81	64 ± 3	10 ± 2	84

[†]Room temperature (RT)

Table 1: Flexural properties of interleaved laminates.

Figure 2: Flexural modulus vs. flexural strength of the interleaved composites at room temperature.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The interleaf/CFRP interface in carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites with controllable stiffness was investigated. Premature flexural failure occurred when polystyrene interleaved composites were tested at room temperature in three point bending. This was due to poor bonding at the polystyrene/CFRP interface. This issue was resolved by exchanged the PS layers with styrene maleic anhydride interleaf films. Laminates were tested at room and elevated temperature (140°C) using flexural tests to verify the improvement in the interleaf/CFRP bond. Laminates containing SMA interleaf layers had significantly higher flexural strengths than composites containing pure PS layers.

REFERENCES

- [1] I.K. Kuder, A.F. Arrieta, W.E. Raither and P. Ermanni, Variable stiffness materials and structural concepts for morphing applications, *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, **63**, 2013, pp. 33-55.
- [2] C. Thill, J. Etches, I. Bond, K. Potter and P. Weaver, Morphing skins, *The Aeronautics Journal*, **112**, 2008, pp. 117-139.
- [3] A.Y.N. Sofla, S.A. Meguid, K.T. Tan and W.K. Yeo, Shape morphing of aircraft wing: Status and challenges, *Materials and Design*, **31**, 2010, pp. 1284-1292.
- [4] C. Tridech, H.A. Maples, P. Robinson and A. Bismarck, High performance composites with active stiffness control, *ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces*, **5**, 2013, pp. 9111-9119.

- [5] W. Raither, A. Bergamini, F. Gandhi and P. Ermanni, Adaptive bending-twist coupling in laminated composite plates by controllable shear stress transfer, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **43**, 2012, pp. 1709-1716.
- [6] F. Gandhi and S.G. Kang, Beams with controllable flexural stiffness, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **16**, 2007, pp. 1179-1184.
- [7] G. Murray and F. Gandhi, Multi-layered controllable stiffness beams for morphing: energy, actuation force, and material strain considerations, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **19**, 2010, 045002.
- [8] F. Gandhi, G. Murray and S.G. Kang, Flexural stiffness control of multilayered beams, *AIAA Journal*, **47**, 2009, pp. 757-766.
- [9] H.A. Maples, S. Wakefield, P. Robinson and A. Bismarck, High performance carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composites with controllable stiffness, *Composites Science and Technology*, **105**, 2014, pp. 134-143.
- [10] G. Heness, M. Stevens and B. Dossett, The effect of surface treatment on delamination for a nylon interleaving material, *Material Forum*, **31**, 2007, pp. 90-95.